

Comparative analysis of high-rise building behaviour using base isolation and virtual outriggers

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Abstract: There is a huge demand for housing to meet shelter needs as a result of the growing population and land shortage. For engineers, meeting the housing demand in the face of this expanding population has become a major challenge in recent years. The construction of tall buildings, or high-rise buildings (HRBs), is thought to be an efficient way to address this problem. Wind and seismic forces are important considerations in high-rise building design, which increases the susceptibility of structures to vibrations. Numerous lateral load-resisting systems, such as shear walls, belt trusses, outriggers, base isolation, staggered trusses, and tube-in-tube systems, are available to control these vibrations or displacements. One common method used to shield high-rise buildings from seismic forces is base isolation. To separate the superstructure from the substructure, a variety of base isolators or bearings are used nowadays, including ball and roller bearings, curved slider bearings, high-damping bearings, elastomeric bearings, lead rubber bearings (LRB), and pendulum bearings. Nonetheless, outrigger systems are thought to be among the best ways to improve high-rise buildings' overall stability and lateral stiffness. ETABS 2020 software is used in this study to model and analyze a 30-story grid-plan high-rise building in seismic zone V with and without the virtual outrigger and base isolation system. LRB is used as the base isolation system, and a steel belt truss is used as the virtual outrigger. A response spectrum analysis is conducted to evaluate various structural response parameters, including storey displacement, storey drift, overturning moment, base shear, and modal time period under earthquake loads.

Key Words: High rise building; outrigger; base isolation; seismic zones; structural responses; storey displacement; storey drift; overturning moment; base shear; modal time period.

1. Introduction

The need for tall buildings has increased significantly as a result of urban migration, land scarcity, and population growth. Because of this, there are more high-rise structures being built all over the world, which creates new difficulties. Humanity has always been captivated by heights and has constantly strived to achieve new heights, both literally and figuratively. However, buildings tend to become less rigid as they get taller. The power and prestige of a civilization have often been demonstrated through impressive and massive constructions, from the ancient pyramids to modern skyscrapers. Unfortunately, tall buildings are generally designed to be lightweight and flexible, making them prone to vibrations due to low damping. Drift issues become more important as buildings get taller, changing the design criteria from allowable stress to member efficiency determined by maximum lateral displacement. Finding efficient ways to reduce the motion of large structures in order to maintain structural integrity and occupant comfort is therefore one of the most important problems facing civil engineers today.

1.1 Outrigger technique

i) Lateral load resisting systems

For high-rise structures to remain stable when subjected to lateral loads like wind and earthquake loads, a lateral load-resisting system is necessary. The lateral loads acting on buildings increase in height along with them, and the impact of these lateral loads on the structure gets worse. Depending on the type of building, several structural systems are offered to help the structures withstand lateral loads. The most widely used techniques for lateral load resistance are belt truss, diagrid systems, shear walls, bracings, frames, staggered truss, and tube in tube.

ii) Behaviour of outrigger

The outrigger system's operation is straightforward. The onset of axial forces in the external columns reduces the rotation of the central core when the lateral load (such as seismic or wind) is occurring on the structure. Consequently, leeward columns would develop compressive force, and windward columns would develop tensile force. The moment at the outrigger position is also drastically diminished at the same time. Exterior columns are

perfectly attached to prevent the rotation of outriggers. Buckling restrained brace (BRB) is inserted to resist the tension as well as compression in the building owing to ground excitation.

1.2 Base isolation technique

i. Purpose of base isolation

A suspension system is introduced between the base and main structure as part of the state-of-the-art technique known as base isolation, which separates the superstructure from the substructure. The two most common loads that necessitate lateral design of a structure are winds and earthquakes. The inertial forces brought on by an earthquake are inversely correlated with the structure's mass and ground acceleration. The most common approach to managing seismic demand is to increase a structure's elasto-plastic strength or ductility. The goal of base isolation is to decrease seismic demand rather than to increase capacity. It is impossible to control ground motion, but we can change the demand on the structure by lowering the motions that are conveyed to the structure from the foundations.

ii. Principle of base isolation

The fundamental idea underlying base isolation is that the structure's or a building's response is altered such that the ground below can move with little to no motion being transmitted to the structure above.

iii. Type of base isolation devices

There are six types of base isolation devices used widely such as elastomeric bearings, high damping bearings, lead rubber bearings (LRB), curved slider bearings, pendulum bearings, ball and roller bearings etc.

2. Methodology

In the present study, analysis of a 30 storied RCC high rise building is carried out by considering it is located in the earthquake zone V; and hard soil. ETABS software models the building structure both with and without a virtual outrigger (belt truss outrigger) and base isolation system (LRB).

2.1. Modelling

According to IS 16700- 2017 criteria for tall concrete buildings. Cl no 7. Criteria used for modelling the building in software:

1. Rigid end offsets of linear members in the joint region, when centerline modeling is adopted.
2. Floor diaphragm flexibility as applicable
3. Cracked cross sectional area properties
4. P-delta effect.

2.2. Preliminary data.

Geometrical properties as a preliminary data is shown in Table -1. The typical floor plan of the structure and its developed analytical model without and with virtual outrigger is shown in Fig.1 (a), Fig. 1 (b) and Fig. 1 (c) respectively.

Table 1- Preliminary data

No of bays in X and Y direction	7	No of storey	30
Spacing of bays in each direction	4m	Thickness of wall	200mm
Plan dimension of building	28m X 28m	Density of light weight brick	20kN/m ³
Height of each storey	3m	Grade of concrete	M40
Height of bottom storey	3m	Grade of steel	HYSD500

Fig. 1 (a) Typical floor plan of 30 storied building

Fig. 1 (b) Analytical model without the virtual outrigger

Fig. 1 (c) Analytical model with the virtual outrigger

2.3. Section properties for beams, columns, shear walls and slabs

Each 5 storey of building is grouped to achieve economy. Different section properties for beams, columns, shear wall and slabs is shown in Table 2.

Table 2- Section properties of beams, columns, shear walls and slabs

Storey range	Beams at outer periphery of the building and core, beams connected to core (mmXmm)	All other remaining beams (mmXmm)	Columns at outer periphery of the building (mmXmm)	All other remaining columns (mmXmm)	Shear wall (mm)	Slab (mm)
1 st - 5 th	450X580	400X530	700X700	630X630	300	150
6 th – 10 th	400X500	350X450	630X630	600X600	275	150
11 th -15 th	400X550	380X550	600X600	550X550	250	150
16 th -20 th	450X580	300X450	550X550	520X520	225	150
21 th -25 th	400X530	300X400	520X520	475X475	200	150
26 th – 30 th	350X450	250X350	475X475	450X450	200	150

2.4. Preliminary analysis data

Different analysis parameters are shown in Table -. The building is subjected to dead load, superimposed dead load due to walls, tiles and finishing and live load analysed. The dead load of structure takes by itself. Superimposed dead load due to wall is calculated as 4.8kN/m by considering light weight brick with wall thickness 200mm.

Table 3-preliminary analysis data

Earthquake zone (zone factor)	V (0.36)	Damping ratio	5%
Soil type	I (hard soil)	Importance factor	1.5

Wind speed	55m/s	Vertical geometry of building	Cantilever type building
Static analysis method	Equivalent method	Approximate time period	For 30 storey =1.53sec
Dynamic analysis method	Response spectrum	Type of diaphragms	rigid
K1, K2, K3	1,1,1 resp.	Modal combination	SRSS
Type of structure	Special moment resisting frame	No of modes	3 modes for each storey
Response reduction factor	5	P delta effect	Non-iterative- based on mass

2.5. Position of virtual outrigger

Two virtual outriggers are placed in total height of building structure. Virtual outrigger in the form of belt truss is provided at in between the 14th to 15th storey and 29th to 30th storey. Steel ISMB section provided to belt truss outrigger. X type of bracing is used as form of belt truss.

2.6. Nomenclatures Used for designation structural models

There are total 4 structural models made up with the reference of virtual outrigger and base isolation system as follows:

M1: fixed base model without virtual outrigger

M2: fixed base model with virtual outrigger

M3: isolated base model without virtual outrigger

M4: isolated base model with virtual outrigger

2.7. Assumption for designing the LRB

LRB is designed using UBC 1997. Maximum axial column force (1.2DL+1.0LL+Emax) stated in the UBC 1997 obtained from the analysis result of structural models M1 and M2 is used while designing the LRB for structural models M3 and M4 respectively. Different assumptions are made while designing the LRB are listed in the tabular format as shown in Table 4.

Table 4- Assumptions for designing the LRB

shear modulus,G	0.7 Mpa	soil profile type	Hard
design time period TD	1.53 sec	seismic coefficient $C_v=C_vD$	0.516
seismic zone factor Z	0.36	seismic coefficient C_a	0.372
seismic source type	B	choose response reduction factor	5
near source factor N_a	1	damping coefficient B_d or B_m	1
near source factor N_v	1	post yield stiffness to pre yield stiffness ratio for rubber n	0.1
ZN_v	0.36	yield strength of lead	10 Mpa
maximum capable earthquake response coefficient M_m	1.5	maximum shear strain of rubber γ	100%
horizontal time period consider	2 sec	let thickness of shim plates	2.8 mm
horizontal frequency f_h	0.5 Hz	end plate thickness is between 19mm to 38mm	25 mm
set vertical frequency f_v	10 Hz	bulk modulus K	2000 Hz
so provide single layer of rubber (round up to nearest 5)	25 mm	cover from lead to end plate	25 mm

2.8. Properties of LRB

Linear analysis of models is carried out. LRB for model M3 and M4 are designed for maximum column load M1 and M2 respectively. After following the design procedure different properties such as rotational inertia and stiffness of LRB are found. Linear properties of LRB with effective damping 0.05 are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 – Properties of LRB

Model	Column load (kN)	rotational inertia	for U1 effective stiffness (kN/m)	for U2 and U3 effective stiffness (kN/m)
M3	7861	0.88	13501159	13501
M4	7695	0.84	13214749	13215

3. Results and discussion

❖ Results

The analysis result for various structural parameters viz., storey displacement, storey drift, overturning moment, base shear, modal time period under earthquake load incorporating with and without virtual outrigger and base isolation system in seismic zone V for hard soil are shown in the Table- 6.

Table 6– Analysis result for storey displacement, storey drift, overturning moment, base shear and modal time period

Model	Storey displacement (mm)	Storey drift	Overturning moment (kNm)	Base shear (kN)	Modal time period (Sec)
M1	220.41	0.003021	613020	8460	3.687
M2	187.75 (-14.82)	0.002825 (-6.49)	609375 (-0.59)	8469 (0.10)	3.474 (-5.78)
M3	244.03 (9.68)	0.00336 (10)	617656 (0.75)	8460 (0)	4.007 (7.99)
M4	211.52(4.03)	0.00337 (10.35)	614008 (0.16)	8469 (0.10)	3.823 (3.56)

Graphical representation for different structural response parameters viz., storey displacement, storey drift, overturning moment, base shear, modal time period under earthquake consideration to get more acquainted with the analysis results for structural models under consideration are resented below:

Fig.2 – Storey displacement

Fig.3 – Storey Drift

Fig.4- Overturning moment

Fig.5- Base shear

Fig.6- Modal time period

❖ Discussion

Checks of I.S. codes

- 1) Storey displacement – according to IS 16700-2017 limitation criteria or maximum permissible storey displacement is $H/250$ for earthquake load; where, H is total height of building. Hence maximum allowable displacement for structural model is 360mm which is more than the structural model M1, M2, M3 and M4. Thus, the building is safe for maximum storey displacement limit.
- 2) Storey drift- limitation criteria for maximum storey drift as per IS code 1893:2016(part-1, clause 7.11.1) is limited to $0.004h$; where, h is storey height. Therefore, limited value for storey drift is 0.012 ($h=3m$). storey drift value for all structural models are within the permissible limit. Hence the building is safe.
 - Storey displacement: Storey displacement of structural models is controlled by providing virtual outrigger. Storey displacement of model M2 and M4 is less than Model M1. With the application of LRB storey displacement increases that is storey displacement of model M3 is more compared with other structural models under consideration.
 - Storey drift: Virtual outrigger is drift controller that is its use reduces the storey drift of model. Storey drift increases for models with LRB. Model M2 has less drift value than model M1, model M3 and model M4.
 - Overturning moment: Model with only virtual outrigger reduces the overturning moment as it is acting as lever arm which produces the anti-clockwise moment. Models with LRB does not shows any significant change as compared with moment resisting frame.
 - Base shear: Base shear is a function of seismic weight. As presence of virtual outrigger in the model M2 and M4 it contributes the more base shear value than model M1 and M3. There is no any significant impact of LRB on the base shear value.
 - Modal time period: Outrigger stiffen the building, hence the time required for the first sway due to ground excitation is less. Whereas due to base isolation system building becomes more flexible, therefore time required for the first sway of building under earthquake motion is more.

4. Conclusion

Storey displacement of model M2 decreases by 14.82%, M3 increase by 9.68% and M4 increases by 4.03% as comparing with model M1. Storey drift of model M2 decreases by 6.49%, M3 increase by 10% and M4 increases by 10.35% as comparing with model M1. Overturning moment of model M2 decreases by 0.59%, M3 increase by 0.75% and M4 increases by 0.16% as comparing with model M1. Base shear of model M2 increases by 0.1%, M3 increase by 0% and M4 increases by 0.1% as comparing with model M1. In comparison to model M1, the modal time period of model M2 decreases by 5.78%, that of model M3 increases by 7.99%, and that of model M4 increases by 3.56%.

We can infer from the analysis that the base isolation system and virtual outrigger operate in opposition to one another, which is a structural response parameter. storey displacement, storey drift, overturning moment and modal time period decreases with virtual outrigger whereas increases with base isolation system with and without

virtual outrigger. Virtual outrigger is efficient lateral load resisting system which controls storey displacement and storey drift. Base isolation system (LRB) offers flexibility to structure who increases the time required for the first oscillation of structure due to ground excitation.

References

1. Base isolation system, access online [Base isolation](#)
2. Seismic performance of buckling – restrained brace outrigger system in various configurations, access online [Behaviour of outrigger](#)
3. A. Naik and S. Maru, Seismic analysis of high rise building having lateral load resisting elements with and without base isolation, *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 10 (4), (2022)
4. A. Hebbar and K. Kamath, Seismic performance of outriggers equipped with lead rubber bearing base isolation system, *Gradiva Review Journal*, 7 (7), (2021)
5. A. Umare and P. Shirawadekar, Analysis and Design of G+10 Building by Injecting Base Isolator System in Structure Using ETABS 2013 software, *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 9 (8), (2020)
6. N. Mithbhakare and P. Kumbhar, Analysis of high-rise building using RCC virtual outrigger system, *International Journal of Engineering Applied Science and Technology*, 5(7), (2020)
7. R.Raut and H. Dahake, Comparison of outrigger system in tall building, *Journal of Engineering Science*, 11(7), (2020)
8. T.Subramani and K.Murali, Analytical study of tall building with outrigger system with respect to seismic and wind analysis using ETABS, *International Journal of Engineering and Technology, SPC*, 7(3.10),(2018)
9. A. Gadkari and N.Gore, Performance of multi outrigger structural system in geometrically irregular shaped high-rise building, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, 5(7),(2018)
10. S. Ambasta, et al., Analysis of Base Isolated Building (Lead Plug Bearing) in ETABS, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 5 (1), (2018)
11. S. Nasir and A. Patil, Lateral stability analysis of high rise building with the effect of outrigger and belt truss system, *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3 (8), (2016)
12. S. Sukhdev, Optimum position of outrigger in G+40 RC building, *International Journal of Science and Technology*, 2 (10), (2016)
13. O. Mohammad and O. Najim, Outrigger system to mitigate disproportionate collapse in building structures, *World Multidisciplinary Civil Engineering Architectural Urban Planning Symposium, ELSEVIER, Procedia Engineering* 161, (2016)
14. Shivacharan. et al., Analysis of outrigger system for tall vertical irregularities structures subjected to lateral loads, *International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology*, 4 (5), (2015)
15. S. Kogilgeri and B. Shanthapriya, A study on behaviour of outrigger system on high rise steel structure by varying outrigger depth, *International Journal of Research In Engineering And Technology*, 4(7), (2015)
16. A. Mulla and B. Srinivas, A study on outrigger system in a tall R.C. structure with steel bracing, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Technology*, 4(7), (2015)
17. S. Shaikh and P. Murnal, Base Isolation at Different Levels in Building, *Journal of Civil Engineering and Environmental Engineering*, 2 (10), (2015)
18. S. Fawzia et al., Deflection control in composite building by using belt truss and outriggers systems, *World academy of science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Structural and Construction Engineering*, 4 (12), (2010)
19. Z. Bayati et al., Optimized use of multi-outriggers system to stiffen tall buildings, *The 14th world Conference on Earthquake Engineering*, 12 (17), (2008)
20. P. Nanduri et al., Optimum position of outrigger system high-rise reinforced concrete buildings under wind and earthquake loading, *American journal of engineering research*, 2 (8), (2008)